

A Review on Causes and Consequences of ARAB SPRING

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Abstract

This research aims to investigate the reasons behind the Arab Revolts in Middle Eastern nations. Additionally, it emphasizes the occurrences of the civil upheavals that resulted in the overthrow of several kings. This essay also makes predictions about the effects of these massive protests on the area and the states nearby. It also looks at how social networking sites were used throughout these events and how it contributed to the dissemination of information about their activities. As a result of these uprisings and civil unrest, long-time autocratic rulers in Tunis, Libya, and Egypt were overthrown, and certain socioeconomic rights were granted to those living in Oman, Saudi Arabia, Morocco, and Bahrain. Additionally, it looks at how Tunis was among the Arab Spring's victims and how it was able to reap the true benefits of the movement whilst other states were unable to do so.

Keywords: Arab Spring, Continuous emergency, Social Media, Civil clashes.

Introduction:

The term "Arab Spring " was first used in US political Academic Journal, "Foreign Policy " by Marc Lynch, an American Political Scientist in his article. The Arab Spring was a series of anti-government demonstrations, uprisings and armed struggle that spread in Middle-east and North-African Arab world's countries in the early 2010s. It began with protests in Tunisia in response to repressive regimes and low living standards. Protests from Tunisia then spread to five other countries: Libya, Egypt, Yemen, Syria and Bahrain where the ruler was ousted or there were major uprisings and social violence, including riots, civil wars or uprisings. Protests erupted in Morocco, Iraq, Algeria, Iranian Khuzestan, Lebanon, Jordan, Kuwait, Amman and Sudan. Minor protests took place in the Djibouti, Mauritania, Palestine, Saudi Arabia, and Moroccan occupied western Sahara. One of the main slogans of the protesters in the Arab world is "People want to overthrow the government" (Abu Sharif, 2014).

Figure 1: Government overthrown protests and militant actions done in following territories.

Causes of the Arab Spring

1-Economical Cause

Economical Cause can be subdivided into,

(i) Role of Global Crises

In the Middle East and North Africa, the economic situation is quite different. Oil-rich countries in the region have greater GDP levels than the rest of the region. Libyan and Algerian economies are based on oil and gas exports, while Egypt, Morocco, and Tunisia rely on industry and tourism (Al-karam, 2011)

North African countries have implemented economic reforms with the assistance of the IMF and the World Bank (Khalili, Schwedler, Zartam, & Eid, 2011). Government intervention in the national financial system was diminished as public institutions were privatised. All of the countries in the region were hit by the financial crisis of 2008-9. The amount of industrial items sent to Europe and America from these countries has declined (Muller & Hubner, 2014).

(ii) Role of food crises

Food and inflation crises have occurred in the past as a result of political instability, particularly in countries that rely on other countries. Inflation caused uprisings in poor nations such as Yemen, Morocco, Tunisia, and Egypt in 2007-08. The inflation rate soared from 25% to 30% two years before the Arab Spring (Muller & Hubner, 2014). Oil-rich countries were largely unaffected because they maintained a price-procurement equilibrium. This entire situation has resulted in political unrest in the region (Ansari & Daniel, 2012).

(iii) Role on Unemployment

Due to a drop in manufacturing products exports, unemployment has grown in nations such as Morocco, Tunisia, and Egypt. Unemployment was high among young people. Unemployment was particularly high among young women (Barany, 2011). Arab countries had the lowest female participation in the labour force worldwide. The Arab Spring was mostly fueled by unemployment (Tucker, 2012).

Table 1:

Variables	Algeria	Egypt	Morocco	Tunisia
Unemployment (total) ^c	10.0	8.9	9.1	13.0
Unemployment (female) ^d	10.1**	22.6*	10.5*	—
Youth unemployment	21.5	24.8	17.6	29.4
Youth unemployment (female) ^b	—	47.9**	19.4	—

Note: ^aOn labour force 15–24 years; ^bon female labour force 15–24 years; ^con total labour force; ^don total female labour force. No data for Libya; *2008; **2007.

Source: World Bank, World Development Indicators and ILO, Statistical update on Arab states and territories and North African countries, May 2011.

2-The Social Causes

(i) The youth Badge education and Democracy

True, the Middle East and North Africa had political and economic differences, but young people between the ages of 15 and 29 made up more than a third of the population in both regions. And the quality of education in these countries has improved during the last three decades. That is why the Arab Spring mobilized the youth in the fight for demarcation, political, and economic rights (BBC Report, 2012).

Insurgencies, political radicalism, and civil strife are more likely to develop in young nations, according to history. During the 1990s, countries with a young population were three times more likely than those with an older population to experience civil unrest (Terrill, 2011).

(ii) Political Freedoms & Economic Inequalities

Popular Arab demonstrations are also regarded from a political standpoint, with people demanding more political and civil rights. One of the reasons for the Arab Spring is that people asked that their governments enhance their political, social, and economic rights, as well as provide education and job opportunities, but the governments did not listen.

Liberty, the ability to vote, and freedom of expression were among the demands of the people. They desired to alter the governing elite, which reaped several rewards such as Gaddafi and Hosni Mubarak (Tucker, 2012).

(iii) The role of Social Media

During the Arab Spring, relevant nations, particularly Tunisia, Libya, and Egypt, attempted but failed to suppress the flow of news via social media. The Arab Spring was largely fueled by the Internet and social media, particularly Facebook and Twitter. Many networks, like Al Jazeera and Al Arabiya, broadcasted the revolution's news around the world. During the Arab Spring, the use of social media increased in Egypt and Tunisia. Egyptian President Hosni Mubarak has ordered a five-day social media blackout (Ansari & Daniele, 2012).

In locations where protests were taking place, the Gaddafi regime also cut off phone service. The Arab Spring was dubbed the "Social Network Revolution" by the media. But despite all these measures, social media played a role in the Arab Spring and spread the word all over the world (Tucker, 2012).

(iv) Discrimination against ethnic and religious Minorities

Religious and ethnic prejudices against minorities were common in the region, and this trend was accelerating, culminating to the Arab Spring. People of various cultures and religions coexisted in the Middle East. Minorities were persecuted on religious and ethnic grounds in several locations. The Shia and Sunni sects are primarily located in the Middle East, but other historic religions and sects exist as well. Ancient ethnic groups and religions include the Alwite in Syria, Druze in Lebanon, Baha in Iran, and Copts in Egypt (Shoreward & Al karam ,2011).

Arabs make up the majority of the population, while Turkmens, Armenians, Assyrians, and Kurds make up the minority. Ethnic minorities, such as Kurds and Turkmens, have been persecuted by Saddam Hussain in Iraq at various times. One of the main causes of the Arab Spring was discrimination against ethnic and religious minorities (Roza ,2012).

3-Self-Immolation

All of the preceding factors for the Arab Spring are first and foremost. The suicide of a young man called Muhammad Bouazizi, on the other hand, heralded the start of the Arab Spring. Mohamed Bouazizi was a Tunisian peddler who set fire to himself after being abused by a female municipal officer (Shoreward & Al karam ,2011).

This was the incident that rocked the inhabitants of all the kingdoms to their core. As a result, a wave of fury swept the Middle East and North Africa, resulting in the Arab Spring movement (Roza, 2012).

Goals

There were certain destinations for the people participating in the Arab Spring. There were certain rights that they wanted to get from their governments, the most important of which are as follows:

- Democracy
- Free Election
- Economic Freedom
- Human Rights
- Employments
- Regime Change

Methods

The goals set by the Arab Spring are described in the above lines. The following are the ways or means adopted by the people participating in the Arab Spring to achieve these goals.

Civil Disobedience

- Civil Resistance,
- Demonstrations,
- Defection,
- Insurgency,
- Internet
- Activism,
- Mutiny,
- Protests,
- Protest
- Camps,
- Revolution,
- Riots,
- Self-immolation,
- Silent
- Protests,
- Sit-ins,
- Media Activism,
- Strike Actions,
- Urban Warfare,
- Uprising etc.

Major events

Bahrain

On February 14, 2011, protests erupted in Bahrain, calling for political freedom and respect for human rights rather than overthrowing the monarchy. The main reason was the minority Sunni population's control over the majority Shia community. The events in Tunisia and Libya had an impact on protesters. Initially, all of the protests were peaceful, but they became more violent once official institutions employed indiscriminate force against the demonstrators. On March 15, King Hamad bin Isa Al Khalifa declared a state of emergency throughout the country, which lasted until June 1. Shiites' homes were searched at this time, and they were imprisoned and tortured. However, this revolutionary movement did not produce any important achievements in the end (Al Karam, 2014).

Egypt

Inspired by the Tunisian revolutionary movement, the Egyptian people also took to the streets against the government. Protests broke out in Egypt on January 25, 2011 and continued for the next 18 days. The administration tried but failed to put a halt to the protests. As a result, Egyptian President Hosni Mubarak was forced to retire, and the Egyptian army took control of the country, selecting Assam Sharaf as Prime Minister. For grave human rights breaches, the former president and interior minister were sentenced to life in jail. Mohamed Morsi, Hosni Mubarak's successor, was deposed in July 2013, and the military regained control of the country. According to international sources, Egypt's condition has worsened as a result of the Arab Spring. The country is still at its lowest position in history ten years after the Arab Spring (New York Times, 2010).

Libya

Protests broke out in Libya on February 15, 2011. On February 18, the opposition took control of Libya's second largest city, Benghazi. The government tried to regain control of the city but failed. Protesters reached Tripoli, Libya's capital, on February 20. On television, Libya's leader Saif al-Islam Colonel Muammar Gaddafi warned demonstrators that if they continued to demonstrate, the country would descend into civil war. The United Nations passed a resolution on March 17 declaring Libya a "no fly zone" and ordering public safety measures. France, the United States, and the United Kingdom entered Libya two days later to bomb Gaddafi's army. The alliance now includes 27 countries from the Middle East and Europe. Anti-Gaddafi troops took control of Tripoli's capital after months of warfare, and Colonel Muammar Gaddafi was slain. Libya has been a war since Colonel Muammar Gaddafi's death. The civil war that started ten years ago is still going on (Shoreward, 2011).

Syria

Protests broke out in Syria on January 26, 2011, when a police officer humiliated a man on Al –Harika Street and arrested him. When people took to the streets to demand his release, the government used all available resources to torture and arrest more than 3,000 people. Fifteen children were also arrested from Dara. On April 18, 2011, people demanded the resignation of Bashar al-Assad, but the Syrian army continued its brutal crackdown on protesters, resulting in 136 deaths on July 31. On August 5, protesters staged another demonstration with the slogan "God with us", killing 11 more people. As a result, the Arab Spring in Syria turned into a civil war that continues to this day (Tucker, 2012).

Tunisia

On December 17, 2011, a young man named Mohamed Bouazizi from Tunisia, fed up with poverty and humiliation, set he on fire, sparking a wave of outrage across the country. In Tunisia, large numbers of people took to the streets against the government. As a result, the 23-year rule of Zine El Abidine Ben Ali came to an end. A state of emergency has been declared across the country. A new government was formed and a new constitution was drafted. The people got basic rights. Tunisia was the country from which the Arab Spring began and spread. With the help of the Arab Spring, democracy came to Tunisia and the common man was represented (Jang, 2010).

Yemen

Protests erupted in January 2011 in northern and southern Yemen. Protests in the north were against President Saleh's support for al-Qaeda, human rights abuses, and the violation of northern natural resources. The people of the other part had come out against the amendments in the constitution, economic situation and corruption. But later they demanded the resignation of Ali Abdullah Saleh. The weeks-long protests resulted in Saleh resigning and handing over government affairs to Vice President Abdrabbuh Mansur Hadi. Houthi rebels later overthrew Hadi's government in 2015, sparking a civil war and Saudi intervention that continues to this day (Dawn, 2011).

Consequences

1-Removal of Authoritarian Rulers from Tunis, Libya, And Egypt

Most of the countries in the Middle East and North Africa had monarchies that had been going on for decades. The first and most important step in the Arab Spring was to remove those kings, in which they were largely successful.

Some have apparently achieved democracy, but most have not yet achieved democratic values. Tunisia's president, Zine El Abidine Ben Ali, was the first Arab ruler to be deposed as a result of the Arab Spring (Kareem Fahim, 2011).

After Tunisia, Libya became the target of the Arab Spring, and Colonel Muammar Gaddafi was deposed and assassinated. Hosni Mubarak, who was on the throne of Egypt, also had to wash his hands of the throne. Many

other Arab rulers resigned as a result of the popular uprising, but despite the Arab Spring, democracy did not find a place in these kingdoms. (Asser 2011).

2-Grant of Political and Social Rights

After analyzing the fate of Bin Ali, Gaddafi and Hosni Mubarak, the rulers of Oman, Saudi Arabia, Morocco and Bahrain started giving economic, political and social rights to their citizens. Their actions prevented locals from following in the footsteps of neighboring countries. The ongoing war in Yemen and Syria is also the result of the Arab Spring (Asser, 2011).

3-Development of Public Political Sphere

Despite the negative effects of the Arab Spring, the main positive aspect of it was that political harmony was created among the Arab countries, which resulted in the emergence of political consciousness among the common people and a training to assert their rights. Now people started talking about national politics in public gatherings and giving their opinions about their future. Although full democracy did not emerge in the Middle East, its seeds were sown by the Arab Spring, which will one day emerge (Fahim, 2011).

4-Impact on the surrounding States

When a powerful man like Hosni Mubarak was defeated, the hearts of the rulers of other neighboring countries were also shaken, and they too were in danger of losing their thrones. The rulers of Saudi Arabia and Morocco paid special attention to their subjects in order to maintain peace and prosperity. The Saudi Shah, King Abdullah, announced a US\$ 36 billion package to his subjects so that they would not be part of the revolution. Morocco's King Mohamed VI also took precautionary measures and introduced new laws, which led to elections for a new constitution and parliament across the country (Jang, 2012).

5-Impact on Arab league and GCC

The Arab League, which was plagued by internal strife, played a key role during the Arab Spring. Some members of the Arab League also showed double standards, with some standing with the ruling class and some with behind-the-scenes protesters. The Gulf Cooperation Council sent its troops to evacuate Yemeni President Ali Abdullah Saleh. Due to the Arab Spring, many reforms were also made in GCC (Roza, 2010).

6-International Reactions

The Arab Spring is seen as a step towards democratic values in the Middle East and North Africa. As the revolutionary movement in the Arab Spring progressed, the world's attention turned to it. The world's major powers have taken steps to protect their own interests.

China and Russia had invested heavily in Libya's oil reserves, so they sided with Col. Muammar Gaddafi, while the United States, with its NATO alliance, was active against it. Gaddafi was assassinated by the American Alliance and the opposition. In Syria, on the other hand, Russia sided with Bashar al-Assad to protect its interests (Al Watan, 2010).

Conclusion

This paper explained what the Arab Spring was, when it happened and how it happened. Most of the countries in the Middle East and North Africa were under the rule of the authoritarians. The king considered himself the representative of the people and had complete control over everything. The people of these countries rallied against the kings through protests and uprisings, which forced Tunisian President Zine El Abidine Ben Ali, Libyan President Colonel Muammar Gaddafi, and Egyptian President Hosni Mubarak to abdicate. Colonel Muammar Gaddafi was assassinated by NATO and the people (Syrian Times, 2012). As a result of the Arab Spring, although many rulers have resigned, democracy has not yet been established in these countries. Other human rights have improved. It would be premature to discuss the full results of the Arab Spring, "Whether the

Arab Spring was a complete success or not", because some secrets used to consume time to unfold (Tishreen, 2010).

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